

ISSN 2455-393X

Journal of the English Literator Society

Volume 12 Issue 1, January 2026 | www.jels.in

Research Article

Resistance against Patriarchy and Political Oppression: A Comparative Study of Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi* and Isabel Allende's *The House of the Spirits*

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Published online: 5 January 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18145638>

ABSTRACT

Literature serves as a mirror to every nuance of change, providing the key to the labyrinth of history. Bengali author Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi* (1978) is narrated in the context of the Naxalite movement in British India. Chilean author Isabel Allende's debut Spanish-language novel, *The House of the Spirits* (1982), is set during the repressive regime of Augusto Pinochet. Although these novels are set in different national contexts, they give voice and visibility to women's struggles and convey the interplay of politics, patriarchy, and the brute force of State power. The female protagonist Draupadi in Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi* and Alba in Allende's *The House of the Spirits* are victims of sexual violence perpetrated by state authorities for political reasons. The intersection of gender, violence, and political circumstances is central to the stories of the people from the periphery, as Kimberle Williams Crenshaw proposes that a particular section of society is marginalized by oppression based on different types of identity markers, such as race, gender, class, sexual orientation, religion, etc. The assaults on Alba and Draupadi represent acts of terror to gain control over not only isolated women but also the communities of women in general. Despite the hardships they endure, both characters demonstrate resistance that defies their victimization.

Alba's inner strength and Draupadi's courageous rebellion highlight the layered nature of female agency within oppressive circumstances. The depiction of their suffering, followed by defiance in the face of fear, offers a powerful commentary on the potential for reclaiming agency in mid-1970s Bengal and the early 1980s Chilean context of systemic oppression. By comparing the experiences of the female protagonists through the lens of intersectionality, this study highlights common themes of marginalisation, suffering, and resilience, while also acknowledging the distinct cultural and political contexts within each narrative.

KEYWORDS: Intersectionality, Marginalized, Class, Gender, Representation

FULL PAPER

Introduction

Mahasweta Devi (1926-2016), an eminent Indian author and social activist, penned works in Bengali. Her prolific writings poignantly captured the plight and the systemic inequities encountered by India's indigenous populations. Her writings reflect those voices that are largely isolated from the mainstream and criticize the manipulative political games that seek to suppress the spirit of those who fight against oppression. She writes,

“The sole purpose of my writing is to expose the many faces of the exploiting agencies. That the mainstream remains totally oblivious of the tribal situation furthers that burning anger... I believe in anger, in justified violence, and so peel the mask off the face of India which is projected by the government, to expose its naked brutality” (Devi, ix-x).

Her short story *Draupadi* brings forth these harsh realities hidden behind socioeconomic and political barriers. This story was first published in *Agnigarbha* in 1978. This short story, translated from Bengali to English by Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, is part of Devi's short fiction trilogy, *Breast Stories*, which was published in 1997. The central focus of the narrative centres on Dopdi Mejhen, a tribal woman who was identified as “Naxalite” by the State authority. The term “Naxalite,” also known as “Naxals,” refers to groups that employ violent tactics against influential figures—feudal landlords and others—who exploit impoverished landless labourers and tribal communities. Their mission is to combat exploitation and oppression, aiming for a society free from class divisions and hierarchies. The story unfolds in the tribal regions of Bengal, a recurring backdrop in Mahasweta Devi's works. *Draupadi* (or *Dopdi*

Mejhen) is a wanted Naxalite, pursued relentlessly by the State with a substantial bounty on her head.

In terms of the publication of her work, Mahasweta Devi precedes Isabel Allende. The social and cultural contexts of India and Chile appear to be different. However, they are both from developing nations. These countries are exploited by colonisers and even by local brutal political forces. So, they share the common crisis of having a history of suffering and loss of identity. In such crisis-prone situations, women are always treated as the other or second-class in society. The position and abilities of women are often overlooked. As rightly pointed out by Mathew Arnold, "Everywhere there is a connection. Everywhere there is illustration. No single event, no single literature is adequately comprehended except in relation to other events, to other literatures" (14th November, 1857). The contextualization of literature and the consideration of women's voice and presence have always been regarded as necessary.

Isabel Allende is a Chilean-American author who writes mainly in Spanish. Her works are based on historical events and her own experience. Her debut novel, *The House of the Spirits*, was first published in 1982 in Buenos Aires. Magda Bogin translates it from Spanish to English. It is set against the backdrop of Chile's political turmoil and addresses issues of power, social justice, and the impact of political events. Augusto Pinochet came to power through a military uprising. When he became the ruler, he ordered the murder of Salvador Allende, the previous president of Chile. It is also true that he is the author Isabel Allende's uncle. This political and personal connection is vividly portrayed in the novel. It is a novel about four generations of assertive women and the Trueba family, in which the fourth-generation female character, Alba, experiences repeated and varied oppression by the military dictatorship but ultimately overcomes these challenges with strong determination. She writes in *Writing as an Act of Hope*.

"Now, finally, women are breaking the rule of silence and raising a strong voice to question the world. This is a cataclysm. It is a new literature that dares to be optimistic—to speak of love in opposition to pornography, of compassion against cruelty. It is a literature that's not afraid of colloquial language, of being sentimental if necessary; a literature that searches the spiritual dimension of reality, that accepts the unknown and the unexplainable, confusion and terror; a literature that has no answers, only questions; a literature that doesn't invent history or try to explain the world solely with reason, but also seeks knowledge through feelings and imagination". (Allende, 2007, 166)

Objectives

- This paper tries to portray why the main characters Draupadi and Alba faced oppression by patriarchy and political power.

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- The political state force not only tried to oppress them physically, but they were tortured mentally. They are both impacted by sudden trauma and how it leads them to deal with the situation by not simply succumbing but fighting back against brutal power.
 - These two narratives are situated in different contexts. It's essential to compare the cultural and political contexts that shape the protagonists' experiences and resistance.
 - This paper interrogates how themes of marginalization, suffering, and resilience are represented in these narratives.
 - This study tries to shed light on how literature portrays and questions the connections between gender, violence, and political authority.

Methodology

This paper examines intersectionality as a theoretical framework for understanding how literature from diverse cultural and political contexts portrays the struggle against patriarchy and political oppression. In Feminist theory, intersectionality emerges as a framework for bringing to light the interconnected systems of oppression within hierarchies of power and privilege. Intersectionality focuses on how overlapping multiple social identities, including race, class, gender identity, sexual orientation, and religion, intersect and create systematic disadvantage for the peripheral people. It recognises that identity markers do not exist independently of each other, often resulting in a complex convergence of oppression. It highlights not only the intersection of socially produced lived experience but also considers how experience also depends on the historical and cultural context within which a woman exists. These systematic restriction targets women, continuously reshaping their daily lives. Specifically, it investigates how Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi* and Isabel Allende's *The House of the Spirits* depict the experiences of women who endure and resist sexual violence perpetrated by state authorities. The study seeks to uncover the commonalities and differences in the portrayal of female resistance, agency, and identity formation in these two narratives.

Analysis and Discussion

In Mahasweta Devi's *Draupadi*, the protagonist is Dopdi Mejhen, commonly referred to as Draupadi. She was born when her mother was thrashing paddy as an enslaved person at the house of her master, Surja Sahu. From the beginning of her life, she was cursed as she was born to tribal parents and led a subdued life with her husband Dulna, like a woman in a traditional society. Surja Sahu exploited both Dulna and Draupadi in turn for the paddy, which Dulna's ancestor had borrowed from him. As a tribal woman, she was followed by the lustful eyes of her master, whose mouth

watered when he looked at her (Devi, 1993, 27). However, it was when Surja Sahu and his son denied water to the tribal community, who were dying in the severe drought, that Dopdi, with her husband, protested against the zamindar. She joined Operation Bakuli with her husband and became part of the group of revolutionaries being sought by the army. Her first reaction to the zamindar was 'I will put out his eyes' (27) when captured by the tribal communities.

Then she has become a comrade ready to fight with her baby scythe against guns. She has lost her husband, whom Senanayak encountered. Her husband's corpse is used as bait to capture her. However, she overcomes the police force's undignified and deceitful practices and plans her next move. She remembered what Dulna said to her last time, when they were hiding from the army and working in the Jharkhani belt. "Dear, this is best! We will not be able to have family and children this way. But who knows? Landowners and moneylenders and policemen might one day be wiped out" (30). It was the dream of a free future for the generations to come. The sacrifice was meant to pave the way for younger people to live with dignity and equality.

She was deprived by her own community members, Shomai and Budhna. Whenever somebody challenges the hegemonic power and principles, they are subjugated, abused, and murdered- it is a common principle. When it comes to women as activists, all brutal treatment leads to sexual exploitation. The assault on Draupadi is orchestrated by chauvinistic men with the intent of suppressing femininity. The entire narrative serves as a retaliation against a woman who dared to question the authority of Senanayak, a symbol of patriarchal power. Consequently, every effort is made to quell her spirit and extinguish her revolutionary fervour. This is why she endures collective somatic violence and violence by state-sanctioned authority,

"Then a billion moons pass. A billion lunar years... Trying to move, she feels her arms and legs still tied to four posts. Something sticky under her ass and waist. Her own blood...shaming her, a tear tickles out of the corner of her eye. Her breasts are bitten raw, the nipples torn. How many? Four-five-six-seven" (35).

Draupadi's nakedness in the climax becomes a vivid symbol of how vulnerability can be transformed into strength and defiance. Instead of succumbing to shame, she confronts her oppressors with her naked, wounded body, refusing to cover herself and thereby rejecting the humiliation intended to subjugate her, 'You can strip me, but how can you clothe me again? Are you a man?' (37). Now her resilience creates a sense of fear in Senanayak, and her daunting and bold defiance, 'There isn't a man here I should be ashamed of. I will not let you put my clothes on me. What more can you do? Come on, *kounter* me- come on, *kounter* me' (37).

She recognizes that there is no one to seek revenge against her abusers, she fearlessly defies societal norms as a way of retaliating against the very lawmakers who themselves break the law. Dopdi, directly looking at the eyes of hegemonic masculine powers, subvert the shame attached to the idea of rape. Here, she is not a victim, but an agent with raw individuality who is demanding justice, as in the words of Gayatri Spivak, 'a terrifying super object' (184). Dopdi is doubly marginalized as a woman and as a tribal individual; the state authority and patriarchy both dehumanize her.

In Isabel Allende's *The House of the Spirits*, Alba Trueba, the granddaughter of Clara, is a central character and the narrator of the story. Allende's novel connects family history and national history, attempting to reflect the position of women in both contexts. The patriarch of the Trueba family, Esteban Trueba, who single-handedly tried to control the women's lives in her family and in Tres Marias as a master of that area. His brutal treatment of the peasant women in that area reflects how, as an upper-class man, he took advantage of the lower-class peasant women. Allende's description of the rape of the peasant Pancha Garcia's rape is a graphic description of the way in which he violates all norms of behaviour. She writes,

"Esteban did not remove his clothes. He attacked her savagely, trusting himself into her without preamble, with unnecessary brutality. He realized too late, from the blood spattered on her dress, that the young girl was a virgin, but neither Pancha's humble origin nor the pressing demands of his desire allowed him to reconsider" (Allende, 1993, 64)

This event of the past created a chain of actions that led to torturous sufferings, even of her own granddaughter, Alba. Esteban has served in politics for many years as a member of the conservative party, so there has been resentment and hate for Marxism from the very beginning of his political career. He believes Marxism is evil for society, as it may dismiss the power of people like him. However, her own granddaughter, Alba, actively participates in revolutionary groups that support the lower class. Though she joined this group because of her lover Miguel, who was a leftist leader (354), and according to him, 'violence of the system needed to be answered with the violence of revolution' (354). Eventually, she became a supporter of the revolution and tried her best to fight back against the military dictatorship. However, she was abducted from her own grandfather's home by two men of the military group who brought her to the Colonel. Pancha Garcia's grandson is the colonel. From a very young age, he learns from her grandmother, Pancha Garcia, the dark past of Esteban Trueba. He also discovered that he is a descendant of the Trueba family. However, because of her grandmother's status as a peasant woman, Esteban Trueba rejected her, even silencing her voice. She tells him that though Blanca, Jaime, or Nicolas is accepted as a legitimate child, and if he is given that identity, he would inherit Tres Marias and possibly even become President of the Republic.

When Alba turned fourteen, Esteban Garcia took her grandmother's revenge by forcefully kissing her. She remained silent, 'told no one of that repulsive kiss or the dreams that she had suffered afterwards, in which Garcia appeared as a green beast that tried to strangle her with his paws' (364). She is tortured and raped by him and a group of people,

"A brutal slap knocked her to the floor. Violent hands lifted her to her feet. Ferocious fingers fastened themselves to her breast, crushing her nipples. She was completely overcome by fear. Strange voices pressed in on her. She heard Miguel's name but did not know what they were asking her, and kept repeating a monumental no while they beat her, manhandled her, pulled off her blouse. She could no longer think, could only say no, no, and no, and calculate how much longer she could resist before her strength gave out, not knowing this was only the beginning" (452).

Although they only want to know about Miguel, the guerrilla leader who created havoc against the military regime, Esteban Garcia's personal anger against the upper class, Esteban Trueba, caused a trail of suffering in Alba's life. She is treated as an object who faced violence and torture firstly for her different political stand and secondly because she is a woman. They put her in a dog house where,

"A century later, Alba awoke wet and naked. She did not know whether she was bathed in sweat, water, or urine. She could not move, recalled nothing, and had no idea where she was or what had caused the intense pain that had reduced her to a heap of raw meat" (455).

After so many rapes, "she gave up, deciding to end this torture once and for all. She stopped eating" despite the severe trauma; she finds strength in her family's history and her love for Miguel, a revolutionary (459). Alba's resilience is rooted in her inner strength and her commitment to justice and memory. Alba suffers torture, particularly because she is a woman and knows that rape may very well leave her pregnant. The group of women prisoners also supports her. The women used to sing in the prison; they retained it as a subversive way to stand against the torture. Though this is sometimes regarded as a feminine quality, women make it their weapon. When Alba and other prisoners were transferred to the concentration camp, they created a collective solidarity and sisterhood. Their affinity with each other creates a strong sense of belonging. They began to nurture their choices, experiences, and stories of resilience, even in the conflict-ridden circumstances. Her survival and defiance serve as a testament to the enduring spirit of those who resist tyranny. Alba, as a woman, experiences two faces of patriarchal control: first, familial patriarchy through Esteban, and second, another political patriarchy through the dictatorship.

In Indian society, women from birth are taught to value their chastity, as they are often portrayed as having supreme power equivalent to God. Chilean society is predominantly Catholic, where the concept of the Virgin Mary, portrayed as pure, chaste, and submissive, is often held up as an ideal for women. In Indian mythology and legends, women are glorified for their virtue and feminine qualities. In Chilean society, there are two models of behaviour for men and women respectively: machismo and marianismo. According to Jo Fisher (1993),

“A system of gender relations which exaggerates the difference between men and women according to their so-called ‘natural’ qualities and determines what is acceptable behaviour from each. Whereas, machismo describes men as dominant, authoritative, superior; marianismo perceives women as humble, docile, and compliant”. (420)

So, both societies have prescribed specific roles for males and females. As Judith Butler says, gender identity is a social construction, not a biologically determined fact. If women do not follow these specific rules, they are bound to be punished by patriarchal authority figures. So, the patriarchal societies, which uphold specific regulations and myths about safeguarding women’s honour, often contradict themselves by perpetrating acts that violate the honour of women. Rape represents the act of exertion of power over women through sexual violence in a society where men hold dominance. In the case of rape, societal norms often associate shame and guilt with the victim, particularly women. However, it is the perpetrators- the rapist or victimizers-who should bear the shame for their inhumane actions, rather than placing it on the victim. Women characters in both of these novels challenge the whole notion of shame associated with rape. The female body becomes a space for power and superiority since women are considered vulnerable. However, it is through spirited resistance that women gather the power and voice to challenge such assumptions. The torture is meant to convey a threat and be a deterrent to those who dare to challenge state power. In July 2004, a courageous group of Meitei women in Imphal, Manipur, staged a powerful protest by disrobing in front of the historical Kangla Fort. Their protest was a response to the brutal killing and alleged rape of Thangjam Manorama, a 32-year-old woman who had been taken into custody by the Assam Rifles Personnel. Manorama’s tragic case shed light on military excesses in Manipur. The protest known as Anti-Repression Day remains a significant moment in India’s history, symbolizing the resilience and determination of these mothers who demanded justice for Manorama.

In Mahasweta Devi’s *Draupadi*, the state uses sexual violence as a tool to control and terrorize not only Draupadi but the larger tribal community. Similarly, in *The House of the Spirits*, the military regime uses rape and torture to suppress dissent and instil fear. Both Draupadi and Alba become victims of this violence, but their responses

highlight their resistance to being silenced or shamed. Draupadi's act of standing naked before her captors is a powerful assertion of her agency. She refuses to be seen as a mere victim and instead challenges the authority and power of her oppressors. Dr Krishnaveni (2013), in an article "Draupadi– the Symbol of Retaliation", quotes Miller, saying that empowerment is the only way of change that makes the character of Draupadi iconic.

"The term empowerment refers to a range of activities from individual self-assertion to collective resistance, protest, and mobilization that challenge basic power relations. For individuals and groups where class, caste, ethnicity, and gender empowerment begin when they recognize the systematic forces that oppress them, but act to change existing power relationships" (6)

Alba's resistance is more internal but equally powerful. She endures her suffering and uses her experience to fuel her commitment to political resistance and justice. Both characters demonstrate that resistance can take many forms, from overt defiance to enduring inner strength. The experiences of trauma and the role of memory are central to the identity formation of both protagonists. Draupadi's trauma is a catalyst for her transformation into a symbol of resistance. Her defiance in the face of violence is a way of reclaiming her identity and agency. For Alba, memory serves as a source of strength. Her family's history and her personal experiences shape her understanding of justice and resistance. The act of remembering becomes a form of resistance against the erasure of history and identity.

Conclusion

The position of marginalized tribal women in society cannot be encapsulated easily. Their gender, class, and caste discriminate against them within the community and the nation. Dopdi Mejhen in Mahasweta Devi's short story *Draupadi* experienced every form of discrimination. Whereas Alba in Isabel Allende's *The House of the Spirits* does not belong to the lower class, she is the granddaughter of Senator Trueba; however, as a woman, she becomes a victim of gender discrimination. The patriarchal society continuously suppresses the voices of women by labelling them, on every level, as the 'other' or 'second sex'. Simone de Beauvoir, in her book *The Second Sex* (1949), says that 'one is not born, but becomes a woman' (215); therefore, women are seen as objects that can be reconstructed and corrected at one's convenience. Across the geographies of a capitalist system, the repression of women in all of their agencies reverberates a desire to dominate the feminine body and psyche for the sake of leaving a deep cultural and cognitive scar to fulfil the unresolved contradiction between the owner and the owned. The two stories here epiphenomenally pointed to the wooden legs of the modern juggernaut of capitalist desires, in unflinching, unapologetic light and shade.

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